

The TELOS Collaboration Approach to Reproducibility and Open Science

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Abstract

The TELOS Collaboration is committed to producing and analysing lattice data reproducibly, and sharing its research openly. In this document, we set out the ways that we make this happen, where there is scope for improvement, and how we plan to achieve this. This is intended to work both as a statement of policy, and a guide to practice for those beginning to work with us. Some details and recommendations are specific to the context in which the Collaboration works (such as references to requirements imposed by funders in the United Kingdom); however, most recommendations may serve as a template for other collaborations looking to make their own work reproducible. Full tutorials on every aspect of reproducibility are beyond the scope of this document, but we refer to other resources for further information.

1 About this document

1.1 Introduction

Reproducibility and openness are becoming increasingly important in science. Many fields have experienced some form of replication or reproducibility crisis, where work that had been taken as fact was subsequently found to be based on shaky results that did not stand up to scrutiny. As a fully computational discipline, there is no reason in principle that work in lattice quantum field theory should not be fully reproducible end to end. In some cases, this comes into tension with making optimal use of computing resources; in this document we will make explicit what compromises we make, and where improvements could be made to reduce the impact of these. It is also important that limited public resources not be wasted repeating the same work in multiple contexts because different groups did not have access to each others' data. Our aim is to push forward the boundaries of human knowledge, and the main barriers to this are human and computational capacity; we believe that maximising the amount of our work that we share, and the ability of others to access and build on top of it, is the optimal way to overcome these.

The TELOS Collaboration [1] undertakes Theoretical Explorations on the Lattice with Orthogonal and Symplectic Groups. This document is in part a statement of the way we currently work, in part an indication of the way we intend to work moving forward, and in part a guide to how to do this. Where it makes recommendations or imposes requirements, these are to and on work being performed by the TELOS Collaboration; however, it is our hope that others will draw inspiration from these guidelines and choose to adopt similar ones for their own work. For space reasons, it cannot be a complete guide to every aspect of this process; it instead links to additional material to learn more.

If you find the recommendations presented here useful in your work, we would ask that you cite them in publications that have relied on them. If you wish to adapt this document for your own context, you may do so compatibly with the Creative Commons Attribution License, for example, by including a citation back to this document.

We welcome constructive suggestions for how we can improve our practice, for tools that may help us to achieve our objectives more easily, and for how this document could be made clearer and more helpful, although we do not commit to adopt every good suggestion we receive.

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1.3 How to read this document

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: in Section 1.5, we define a number of relevant terms we will rely on throughout the discussion. In Section 2 we discuss open-access publications, and some other details of the publication process. In Section 3 we discuss how and why we publish our data. In Section 4 we discuss our approach to developing and sharing the workflows used to analyse those data. In Section 5 we outline our aspirations to better enable reproducibility of our HPC-based computations. Appendix A is provided for reference, and also as a summary of the main requirements discussed in the main body.

This document contains relatively densely-packed information, and many of the concepts discussed are tightly linked to each other. It is ordered to give a relatively logical progression; however, the reasoning behind the recommendations in some sections may make more sense in the context of having read later ones. As such, the interested lattice-oriented reader is invited to first skim-read the document from Section 1.5 to Section 5, before going back and re-reading these sections in more detail.

While the primary focus of the guidance is numerical research using lattice quantum field theory techniques; we briefly discuss the applicability of the guidance to other related fields in Appendix B. An interested non-lattice reader might then read Section 1.5, then Appendix B, and then the sections outlined in Appendix B.

1.4 Version history

These guidelines are intended as a living document, evolving as our practice develops and as we progress on achieving some of the aims that are currently aspirational or works in progress. The canonical working version of the document is available from GitHub [2]; more significant updates will also be posted to the arXiv and to Zenodo [3].

v0.1.1 2025-04-02 Explain briefly what the TELOS collaboration is and does. Clarify what to do if a journal says no to the rights retention statement. Clarify some phrasing. Avoid using words reserved in Section 1.5.7 outside of those definitions. Make Data and Software availability statements comply with this guidance. Recommend `---Analysis workflow` rather than `---Workflow` for workflow names, consistent with existing work. Software availability statement in checklist.

v0.1.0 2025-04-02 First version shared publicly via arXiv and Zenodo. Describe version history. Tidy up front matter. Make license explicit. Add Acknowledgments and other end matter. Expand Introduction. Rename HEMCEE to HMCDJ. Fix some typos.

v0.0.6 2025-03-25 Make Appendix B less roundabout.

v0.0.5 2025-02-10 Add dates to version history. Make more explicit statement around who the document is for. Add reference to template repository for workflows. Add appendix discussing applications outside lattice. Mention how to validate against the schema, and require this. Mention software and data availability statements. Correct subsections on testing and publishing to being subsections. Add reading guide. Fix some typos.

v0.0.4 2025-01-28 Incorporate changes from first internal review. Clarify our lack of legal qualifications, and some other language. Explicitly state that UKRI requires CC BY. Recommend a directory structure. Recommend maintaining HDF5 structure consistency. Mention Zenodo command-line uploads. Avoid overfull hboxes. Give an explicit example of code to go in a library. Mention existing provenance tooling. Mention that repositories can continue being used after a Zenodo release. Reformat bibliography to include more links.

v0.0.3 2024-11-29 Add making repo public to checklist.

v0.0.2 2024-11-01 Initial quasi-complete draft.

v0.0.1 2024-10-31 Initial internal draft.

1.5 Definitions

1.5.1 Reproducibility

In our work, we use the definitions of “reproducibility” and associated terms used by the Turing Way project [4]. Specifically, we define an analysis as:

reproducible when another researcher is able to take the same data, perform the same analysis on it, and obtain the same results;

replicable when another researcher is able to produce their own equivalent dataset, perform the same analysis on it, and obtain the same results; and

robust when another researcher is able to take the same data, perform an alternative analysis on it, and obtain results leading to the same conclusions.

Reproducibility is the simplest of these to achieve, and may be considered as trivial; indeed, science is predicated on it, and so work that is not reproducible is of limited value.

1.5.2 FAIR

Data and software tools may be described as FAIR if they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable [5]. Specifically, data and metadata are

Findable if they have a unique, persistent identifier, are described by rich metadata linked back via this identifier, and are indexed or registered in a searchable resource;

Accessible if they are retrievable using a standardised, open communications protocol, allowing for authentication and authorisation where necessary, and where metadata remain available even after associated data are not;

Interoperable if they use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation; if they use vocabularies that follow the same FAIR principles, and use qualified references to other data and metadata; and

Reusable if they are richly described with accurate and relevant attributes, released with a clear and accessible license, associated with detailed provenance, and meet community-relevant standards.

1.5.3 Open Science

Open Science or Open Research is the movement to make all research accessible to all levels of society. This may include not just papers, but also other outputs like data, software, and experimental samples, as well as including those from outside academia in the process of conducting research itself. This can only ever be an ideal to be strived towards, being tensioned against the costs of opening access to limited resources.

1.5.4 Copyright and licensing

In this section we discuss certain aspects of copyright law. It is worth mentioning explicitly that the authors of this document are not legal professionals, and the descriptions below represent our best understanding of the law as it applies in the jurisdictions in which we work; it is not legal advice.

Under copyright law, the default state is that when you provide someone with a piece of copyrighted work or a copy thereof, they have no right to make further copies of it. In a digital world,

this includes many operations that are essential for consuming content, such as downloading a copy of a paper to read. Some actions may be construed as “fair dealing” or “fair use”, where there is no penalty, but many important actions like reusing or building on top of a piece of work require explicit permission. All creative work, including academic papers, data, and software code, automatically receives copyright protection at the moment of its creation, which typically lasts for seventy years beyond the death of its creator.

To avoid each person having to write their own forms of permission (many of which would be found unenforceable on contact with a lawyer), certain organisations have defined standard “copyright licenses” that may be applied to a piece of work to grant others specific permissions regarding what they can do with it and what constraints they have to comply with to benefit from these permissions.

Creative Commons Creative Commons defines a number of licenses suitable for papers and data. These can be recognised as a series of letters starting with “CC”. The most common, and most relevant to our usage, is the Creative Commons Attribution License, CC BY [6]. This gives recipients the right to make and distribute copies of a work, provided that the original author is clearly attributed. This is the license that is mandated by UKRI (unless there are strong reasons to choose a different license), who fund our research in the United Kingdom.

Software Licenses Creative Commons licenses are not considered suitable for licensing software source code, due to concerns around software-specific issues such as patents. Instead, it is better to use specific software licenses. Two common ones are the MIT License [7], which grants rights similar to those granted by CC BY, and the GNU General Public License [8], which imposes an additional requirement that if derivative work is distributed, this distribution is on the same terms.

Much modern gadgetry makes use of MIT- and similarly-licensed software, with a long list of attributions, but likely little support given back to the original authors. GPL-licensed software is less used in this context, due to organisations not wanting to share their proprietary software and potentially give assistance to their competitors. The aim of GPL is that anyone is free to modify and improve the software on their own devices; however, the extent to which this has succeeded is limited.

1.5.5 Paper stages

A paper written by this collaboration typically has a number of stages in its preparation process:

Draft Version worked on by one person, or shared within the collaboration for comment

Preprint Version posted on the arXiv for comments from the community, in advance of submission to a journal.

Author Accepted Manuscript Last version submitted to a journal before acceptance. Incorporates feedback from peer reviewers.

Version of Record Version distributed by the journal. In some cases (for example, in the Journal of High Energy Physics and Proceedings of Science) this will appear near-identical to the Author Accepted Manuscript; in others (such as in Physical Review D) this will have been translated by the editorial office into a different style, likely with one or more rounds of feedback and checking of proofs.

1.5.6 Persistent identifiers

A persistent identifier is an identifier that can be used to refer to a publication, a data asset, or some other object, that is unique within some system, and which provides some guarantee that it will remain available in the future.

The Digital Object Identifier, or DOI, is an example of a persistent identifier. DOIs are issued by journals to refer to articles and by arXiv for preprints, and can also be generated for data and code assets.

1.5.7 Keywords

The key words “*must*”, “*must not*”, “*required*”, “*shall*”, “*shall not*”, “*should*”, “*should not*”, “*recommended*”, “*may*”, and “*optional*” in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC 2119 [9].

2 Publications

2.1 Open Access

There has for a long time been a culture in theoretical particle physics, including in lattice, of sharing preprints openly using the arXiv [10]. More recently, the SCOAP3 agreement has meant that articles published in typical journals for particle physics, such as Physics Letters B and Physical Review D, are made available as open access without additional charge. However, since not all journals or topics are included in this agreement, and to ensure that readers not able to afford journal subscriptions are able to access the corrected versions of papers, our funders now require us to retain rights to “Author Accepted Manuscripts”, that is, the versions of papers as accepted by the journal, after peer review, so that they can be shared under an open license.

To enable this, all papers submitted by the TELOS collaboration *must* include the following text verbatim in the submitted manuscript:

For the purpose of open access, the authors have applied a Creative Commons attribution (CC BY) licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising.

This is referred to as “rights retention”, and is a requirement from our funders UKRI. This *should* be placed in a paragraph titled “Open Access Statement” immediately after the Acknowledgments section. Publishers sometimes remove this statement on publication; this does not affect the process. If a publisher requires retraction of this statement for the paper to be processed, or otherwise attempts to block sharing of the Author Accepted Manuscript, the publication process *must not* continue before the issue is raised and discussed with UKRI.

We *must* also upload either a CC BY licensed Author Accepted Manuscript, or a CC BY licensed Version of Record, to an institutional repository. Where an article has not been covered by SCOAP3, we *must not* upload a non-CC BY licensed Version of Record; the Author Accepted Manuscript *must* be uploaded in that case.

2.2 author.xml

When the INSPIRE database service ingests papers from arXiv, it typically has to take the plain-text author list and parse it into a structured collection of references to known or new authors. This process is error-prone, particularly for larger collaborations, and for individuals whose names collide with common words associated with authorship. (For example, “Ed” is both a name and an abbreviation that may be placed in front of a name to indicate that the latter’s owner is an “editor”. This means that people with the former name frequently have their names incorrectly recorded on INSPIRE.)

To avoid needing to manually send corrections to INSPIRE after each publication, INSPIRE recommends providing a structured, machine-readable set of metadata regarding authorship of a paper. This *should* be done in the form of a file named `author.xml`, having a structure described in Ref. [11].

A template for this file is available in the TELOS Collaboration Resources repository [12]. If this is used, elements marked `TODO` *must* be replaced, and authors’ details *must* be checked, before publication.

When preparing to submit to the arXiv, in addition to the LaTeX sources and assets, two additional files *should* be included:

- The file `author.xml`, prepared as described above.
- The file `author.dtd`, a schema defining the structure that `author.xml` follows, available from Ref. [11].

The file `author.xml` *must* be validated for correctness against the schema, by following the instructions in the documentation at Ref. [11].

2.3 Acknowledgments

It bears reminding that our work is enabled by the work and contributions of many others outside our collaboration, who *must* be appropriately acknowledged in our work.

This includes:

- We *must* specify what software was used to perform the work, both so that the original authors can gain credit, and so that others know which software to use to reproduce our work. This *must* be done in the Software Availability statement, discussed in Sec. 2.4. Additionally, this *may* be done in the section of the narrative where the algorithms and tools are introduced.

- We *must* specify what computing resources were used to perform the work, to comply with our obligations to the HPC facilities, so that we remain able to access them in the future.
- Where we have used open data, we *must* cite the original datasets.
- We *must* acknowledge data storage resources where they have been used.
- We *must* follow all other standard non-computation-specific acknowledgment practices, including acknowledging our funders, and those who have contributing to the work whilst not being authors.

2.4 Additional statements

It might be difficult to fluidly incorporate full information around some of the points discussed above into the main text, or such information might accidentally be removed during editing, or a reader might not easily find it when they look for it. To be maximally explicit, a paper *must* include the following two paragraphs, after the Open Access Statement:

- A paragraph titled “Software Availability Statement”, listing and citing all relevant software used, including version information, and a brief description of what each was used for. This *must* include both software used for data generation on HPC, and software used for subsequent data analysis
- A paragraph titled “Data Availability Statement”, listing and citing all datasets used. This *must* include both open data used (both our previous work, and the work of others), and new data generated for this work (which *must* be published, as discussed in Section 3).

3 Data

The work that we present in publications can represent the output of hundreds of thousands of pounds’ worth of computer time, and terawatt hours of energy. To ensure that this is not wasted, and so that others can reproduce our work and extract additional results beyond our initial work without needing to spend similar resources to regenerate the data, it is vital that we share our data openly. This also enable those quoting our data to do so easily without needing to transcribe numbers, which is liable to introduce errors.

Every peer-reviewed article that presents new data *must* have an associated data release, including the new data that were generated in its preparation. A work that generates no new data, only presenting previously-analysed data, *should not* have a data release. Non-peer-reviewed work, such as conference proceedings, *may* instead refer to the data release of an upcoming peer-reviewed article rather than having a separate data release; however, if such a work will not be forthcoming, a data release *should* be prepared and published.

A publication *must* cite the associated data release using its DOI. Where a publication makes use of data prepared for a previous publication, the associated data release *must* also be cited if it exists. If the publication did not have an associated data release, the data used from it *must* instead be included in the current publication’s associated workflow release.

The data release associated with a publication *should* be published in advance of the preprint being made available, and *must* be published before the paper is published in the journal.

3.1 What to include in a data release

To maximise the utility of a data release to others, a number of classes of data are needed.

3.1.1 Final numbers

To maximise the utility of our results to those looking to make direct use of them, data releases *must* include all numbers that are plotted as points on a graph, and *should* include all parameters for curves fitted using lattice data where these are of use to others. These *must* be provided in CSV format, to maximise ease of use to those who might only be familiar with spreadsheet software. The number of different CSV files *should* be minimised: data that are characterised by the same parameters *should* be combined into a single file. For example, there *may* be one file for numbers relating to individual ensembles, a second file for fit parameters relating to specific values of the coupling, and a third for fit parameters for continuum limit extrapolations.

Currently there is no community-defined metadata schema for structuring such data. Nevertheless, we *should* aim to use a common form for our data to maximise interoperability with others’ work.

- Numbers with single symmetric uncertainties *must* be formatted with columns labelled `{name}_value` and `{name}_uncertainty`.
- Numbers with asymmetric uncertainties *must* use the suffixes `upper_uncertainty` and `lower_uncertainty`.
- Numbers with multiple sources of uncertainty *must* use `uncertainty` or `statistical_uncertainty` as the suffix for the statistical uncertainty, and *must* use suffixes of the form `{uncertainty_type}_uncertainty` for other sources of uncertainty, such as systematic.
- Metrics associated with each other *must* use a common prefix. For example, the mass and matrix element from fitting a pseudoscalar correlation function and the associated $\chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}$ might use column names `ps_mass_value`, `ps_mass_uncertainty`, `ps_matrix_element_value`, `ps_matrix_element_uncertainty`, and `ps_chisquare`.
- Numbers *must* be given to the full machine precision at which they were originally presented, not truncated or rounded.
- Column names *should* be documented in the data release documentation (see Sec. 3.1.6 below).

Note that these constraints apply to data files within the data release, not to numbers presented in the paper (for example, in tables). For example, tables in papers *should not* present numbers to machine precision in almost all cases.

3.1.2 Input files

To enable others to reproduce our work on HPC if they wish to, a data release *may* include the raw input files, if they have been retained in a form that reproduces the original work. If this is done, the release *should* also include sufficient documentation to allow a competent practitioner to be able to use the input files to reproduce the data.

3.1.3 Data from HPC

The TELOS Collaboration’s workflow is typically that some number of gauge ensembles are generated using an HMC-like algorithm, taking significant computational resources and generating substantial data. Then, observables are computed on each configuration in each ensemble, still requiring HPC, but more modest resources, and generating outputs files small enough to process on a workstation. These are then transferred off HPC for final statistical analysis.

Given the constraints of storage, and to enable analysis workflows to be reproducible, our data releases *must* share the observable results that are the inputs to the statistical analysis. This *should* be in as close to its native form as possible; to date, for most of our work, this is text-based log files from HiREP and GRID. Where necessary for filesize reasons, these *may* be thinned by removing redundant, repeated log lines.

To make the download process simpler for a reader only interested in a specific observable, these *may* be structured so that each observable or class of observable is in a separate directory hierarchy. If doing so, it is convenient to maintain the same structure for both the files on the HPC facility and the files used locally for analysis, so that the files can be transferred off HPC with minimal reorganisation necessary. The following directory structure *may* be used:

```
<Gauge Group>/n<Flavour 1 representation><Flavour 1 count>[_n<Flavour 2 representation><Flavour 2 count>]/beta<beta>/m<Flavour 1 representation><Flavour 1 mass>[_m<Flavour 2 representation><Flavour 2 mass>]/<NT>x<NX>x<NY>x<NZ>
```

for example, for Sp(4) with fermions in two representations, this might become

```
Sp4/nF2_nAS3/beta7.2/mF-0.72_mAS-1.14/64x48x48x48.
```

3.1.4 Repackaged data

Since it is tedious to write large amounts of code to parse data from log files, and the reading process itself is relatively slow, if the original output was in a text-based format, a data release *should* also include the input data to the statistical analysis as discussed in Sec. 3.1.3 above, reformatted into a packed format readable by standard libraries.

- The HDF5 format [13] *should* be used for these data.
- A single HDF5 file for all ensembles *should* be preferred to one file per ensemble per measurement, to minimise the effort needed to download and use the data.
- Datasets and groups in the HDF5 structure *must* be given sufficient metadata to identify the specific ensembles they refer to, and what specific observables were computed and parameters used to do so.
- We are currently working on identifying structures for HDF5 files that enable more efficient compression to be achieved. Until this work completes, the HDF5 file structure *should* be consistent with that used for Ref. [14].

3.1.5 Metadata and analysis parameters

As will be discussed in Section 4 below, to ensure that others are able to reproduce our work, it is vital to share the workflows that are used to analyse our data. These workflows will typically rely on knowing information about the data, available in a more compact and quickly-readable form than looking at the headers of each data file separately, and will further rely on information that we choose as part of our analysis. For example, which ensembles do we consider for a particular analysis, or where to we judge the plateau region of an observable to be for each ensemble.

This information is still data, so belongs in the data release rather than being hidden mixed into the analysis workflow.

- A data release *should* contain one or more files containing metadata, and if appropriate, analysis parameters, for the analysis workflow to use as input.
- Metadata and analysis parameters *must* be provided in a plain-text, human-readable format. This *may* be a tabular format such as CSV, or a more structured format like YAML.
- Metadata and analysis parameters *should* be consolidated into as few files as is reasonable, similarly to output numbers discussed in Section 3.1.1.
- The structure of each metadata/parameter file, for example, field or column names, *should* be documented similarly to those for output numbers discussed in Section 3.1.1.
- Metadata/parameter files *may* be prepared using tools; for example, it is more convenient to prepare a large CSV file using a spreadsheet program rather than by hand in a text editor.

3.1.6 Documentation

No matter how careful we are to construct our data releases carefully, we will not be able to remove all ambiguity while maintaining a usefully compact release. As such, it is always necessary write documentation to enable others to understand our releases.

The TELOS Collaboration provides data release documentation in a file called `README.md` included in the data release.

- A data release *must* contain one or more files containing documentation.
- The primary documentation *should* have a filename beginning `README`.
- Documentation *must* be provided in a plain-text, human-readable format. At time of writing, this *should* be Markdown.
- Where multiple documentation files are provided, each *must* be cross-referenced from the main `README`.
- The main `README` *must* provide the following elements:
 - Information on the work the data were produced to enable, including a link to the article(s) in which they were presented.
 - A listing of the files included in the release, and a description of what each file contains.
- Where multiple files (or directories) are grouped into archive files, these archives *should* contain their own `README` files documenting the data formats used for the files therein. Such files *must* be referred to from the main `README` file.
- Descriptions of data formats, columns, etc., *should* be recycled from previous releases where appropriate. (If a release breaks compatibility with the format documented for a previous one, it *should* be carefully considered whether this is necessary and justified, and *should* be explicitly noted in the documentation.)
- Where single files are included in the data release, their structure *should* be documented in the main `README` file.
- Portions of the main `README` file *may* be used as the basis of the data release description.

Markdown For an introduction on how to write Markdown, see for example Ref. [15]. For information on including mathematical expressions in Markdown documents, see for example Ref. [16].

3.2 Where and how to publish a data release

3.2.1 Where to publish

Data releases *must* be published using a platform that provides a persistent identifier (preferably a DOI), and that commits to maintaining availability of the dataset for an appropriate period.

At time of writing, the TELOS Collaboration publishes its data releases using Zenodo [17]. Zenodo provides 50GiB of storage per dataset by default, and allows up to 100 files per dataset. (Zenodo can exceptionally grant up to 200GiB per dataset on a case-by-case basis.) A release *must not* be split into many Zenodo datasets in order to bypass this limit.

3.2.2 Obtaining a DOI before data are ready

It is frequently desirable to have a DOI to put into a manuscript before the data are ready to be uploaded, either to avoid having a “TODO” item in the draft, or because the data release is not ready at time of sharing a preprint. In particular, if a preprint is being released in advance of the data release being ready, it *should* refer to the DOI at which the data will ultimately be made available.

To obtain a DOI from Zenodo before the data are ready:

- Start a new upload in Zenodo.
- Under “Basic Information”, answer “No” to the question “Do you already have a DOI for this upload?”.
- Select “Get a DOI now!”
- Note the DOI that is generated, and add it to the references of the manuscript.
- Add a placeholder file (for example, the draft dataset `README`) and an author to the draft release.
- Click “Save draft”.

The saved draft can then be used as the basis for the full release once it is ready, and citations to it from the draft or preprint will then be correctly resolved.

3.2.3 Structuring the release

Owing to the limitation on the number of files in a release, and the lack of directory structure in Zenodo, some files need to be packaged into archives. However, to maximise the utility of the release to those who might only want a small part of it, thought is needed as to what to group together.

The `README` *must* be a separate file.

CSV files *should* be uploaded as individual files, such that someone wanting to quote a datum from one of them need not download a lot of irrelevant files.

Raw data *should* be packaged into one or more archives. If there are multiple classes of data (for example, HMC logs, gradient flow logs, and correlation function logs), then these *may* be packaged separately. Each archive *should* produce a `raw.data` directory, containing a subdirectory for the specific observable, matching the structure expected by the analysis workflow. As discussed above, each archive *should* contain its own `README`.

Repackaged raw data *should* be uploaded as a single large HDF5 file.

Metadata and analysis parameters *may* be packaged into one or more archives, or uploaded as single files, as appropriate.

Input files *should* be packaged into one or more archives.

Where archives are used, these *should* be ZIP files, not `.tar.gz` files, since the former can be previewed by Zenodo. They *should* use a high compression level, to reduce the storage and bandwidth requirements, in particular for raw data comprising logs, which are naturally storage-inefficient.

3.2.4 Completing the upload form

Files The files discussed above *must* be uploaded. It is *recommended* to upload large files one at a time; concurrent uploads typically fail, and the form needs to be reloaded to delete the failed files and re-upload. For large files, it is *recommended* to use a wired network connection with a high-bandwidth uplink to the Internet. For very large files, the web interface can struggle to complete an upload even with a high-bandwidth uplink. In this case, it is *recommended* to use command-line tools to upload these files, such as `zenodo-upload` [18].

Basic information

- The DOI *should* have been pre-registered per the above.
- The Resource Type *should* be “Dataset”.
- The Title *should* be the title of the corresponding article, followed by “—Data release”. Where the release supports multiple concurrent articles, the Title *may* use both article’s titles, separated by “and”.
- The Creators *must* comprise all authors of the corresponding article(s). Unless otherwise agreed, all authors *should* be listed in the role of “Project member”.
- The Description *should* contain a summary of the README, linking to the relevant article. For example,

```
This release contains all data generated in preparing the paper  
"[paper title]" (insert link).
```

```
It includes two classes of data:
```

- Raw data, as generated from the HMC measurement code running on HPC,
in their native formats.
- Metadata around the analysis of the ensembles, in YAML format.

```
Due to their size, raw gauge configurations are not included in this release.
```

```
Further documentation on the directory structure and file formats is provided  
in the file README.md
```

- An additional Description *must* be added, comprising the Acknowledgments of the relevant paper.
- The License *should* be specified as the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY).

Recommended information This section *may* be left blank.

Funding Grants from the European Union, and from United Kingdom research councils, *must* be listed here. Searching the grant ID surrounded by quotation marks, for example, "EP/V052489/1", typically returns only the grant of interest. (Omitting the quotation marks results in Zenodo including many irrelevant results.) Grants from other countries *may* be listed here also.

Alternative identifiers This section *may* be left blank.

Related works This *should* link to:

- The arXiv preprint, with relation “is described by”.
- The published article, with relation “is described by”.
- The analysis workflow release, with relation “is required by”.

References This section *may* be left blank.

Software This section *may* be left blank.

Publishing information This section *may* be left blank.

Conference This section *may* be left blank.

Domain specific fields This section *may* be left blank.

3.3 Field configurations

Field configurations take significant computational resources to generate, and contain significantly more information than one person or collaboration can extract. As such, we aspire to share our field configurations openly, to maximise the benefit that can be obtained from them. (To this, we apply the constraint that configurations *should not* be retained if the cost of storage outweighs the cost of regenerating them given the input parameters.) In principle, this would also allow data from different collaborations to be analysed many of the same systematics, rather than comparing data that have been computed and analysed with different approximations.

The International Lattice Data Grid (ILDG) [19] defines standards for interoperability and sharing of field configurations. We aim to share our configurations using the UK Regional Grid of the ILDG. Currently this is not in service; further information on preparing and pushing configurations to this service will be provided once it is available.

In the interim, when generating ensembles requiring non-trivial computational effort, we *must* retain sufficient information that the ILDG configuration and ensemble metadata *may* be completed at a later date. This *should* include:

- The gauge group
- The gauge action, associated parameters (e.g. β), and boundary conditions
- The fermion actions, associated parameters (e.g. bare mass), representations, and boundary conditions
- The algorithm used to perform the generation
- The software (including version information) used to perform the generation
- The precision worked at by the software used to perform the generation
- The name and affiliation of the person who performed the generation
- The date and time at which each configuration was generated

4 Workflows

In our data release, we share data from various stages of our computation. However, we *must* also share how data get from one stage to the other. The Royal Society shortly after its founding in 1660 chose as its motto “*nullius in verba*”—take nobody’s word for it— to signify the importance of this. It marked a transition to science being based on reproducibility, where no result could be accepted until others were able to show it for themselves. This laid the foundation for the growth in science over the past centuries.

In principle, sharing the data analysis code used to go from input to output data is not a necessary condition for reproducibility. A sufficiently precise, and accurate, narrative publication could achieve the same result. In practice, however, specifying the level of necessary detail and keeping the actual software used synchronised with this is beyond the capabilities of most authors; in many fields this has led to a “replication crisis” where key findings in a discipline were discovered to be unfounded, as the description of the methodology did not match what was actually done, due either to human error in the analysis process, or imprecise language in the description.

As such, we assert that codifying the analysis performed in data and software, and publishing both of these openly alongside narrative articles, is the *easiest* way to achieve reproducibility of our work. Others looking to apply our techniques (as we would hope they would, if we are doing our jobs properly) can make use of our code directly, or can reimplement based on our descriptions, but cross-check against our implementation for any discrepancies.

Working reproducibly has an initial learning curve, and requires some more up-front setup than diving straight in to fiddling with data and producing plots by hand. However, it pays substantial dividends as the quantity of data you work with increases, the workflows become more complex and interlinked, and the number of projects you work on grows.

In this section we will discuss some of the approaches that we adopt. This will necessarily be incomplete, and our approach is likely to evolve over time, as experience shows us better ways of working, and new tools and technologies become available.

4.1 Workflow essentials

All workflows *must* be developed under version control. In the TELOS Collaboration we use Git for this purpose; if you are unfamiliar with Git, good introductory guides include Refs. [20, 21]. Workflows under development *should* be regularly synchronised with a hosting service, to avoid the only copy being on a laptop that might suffer data loss. We make use of GitHub for this purpose. Workflows *may* be developed under the `telos-collaboration` organisation; if not, they *must* be transferred to this organisation before publishing.

Each workflow repository *must* contain the following files at root level:

- A `README` file, for example `README.md`,
- A `LICENSE` file, and
- A `CITATION.cff` file.

It *should* also contain the following:

- A `.gitignore` file, and
- A `.pre-commit-config.yaml` file.

4.1.1 README

The README of a workflow release *must* contain:

- A brief description of the workflow, including a link to the article presenting the workflow’s output. This *should* be in the form of a DOI.
- A list of prerequisite software needed to be able to use the workflow. This is likely to include Conda, Snakemake (which *may* be installed via Conda), and a LaTeX distribution. This *should* note any “gotchas” that might trip up a potential user, but *should not* give detailed installation instructions that would duplicate the documentation of the software in question.
- Instructions on setting up the workflow. This *should* include how to clone the repository, what data to download from the data release, and where to put it.
- Instructions on running the workflow. This *should* be a single command, and *must* be equivalent to the command that was run to generate the assets presented in the corresponding article. (You *may*, for example, change the parallelisation options to Snakemake is allowed, but *must not* use an entirely different script.)
- Information on the approximate expected runtime of the workflow, and the machine specification on which this estimate is based. (It is useful for a reader to know in advance whether they will need to allocate minutes, hours, or days to the computation.)
- Information on where the output of the workflow is placed.

Additionally, the README *should* contain:

- The DOI of the workflow; this *may* be in the form of a DOI badge. To obtain a DOI from Zenodo prior to releasing it, see the instructions in Section 3.2.2.
- A discussion of the reusability of the workflow. How much of the workflow is expected to be applicable to other contexts, and what work would be needed to do so.

4.1.2 LICENSE

The LICENSE file *should* contain the full text of the license under which the workflow is made available. The TELOS Collaboration uses the GNU General Public License [8] by default. If there are reasons to prefer another license, this *must* be discussed with the collaboration before applying it.

4.1.3 CITATION.cff

To aid tools in generating appropriate citations for our work, we provide metadata on the release in the form of a CITATION.cff file. This is written in the Citation File Format (CFF) [22]. CFF files *may* be generated using the CFFINIT [23] tool, or *may* be based on the skeleton example in the resources repository [12]. If the latter is used, elements marked TODO *must* be replaced, and authors’ details *must* be checked, before publication.

4.1.4 .gitignore

The .gitignore file is a standard mechanism to tell Git what files are (typically) not wanted to be committed to a repository. This *may* be based on a template such as that provided by GitHub [24], but *should* also specify the directories expected to contain data downloaded from the data release, and files output by the workflow. A minimal .gitignore file for a workflow matching the description below might be,

```
# Common temporary files
scratch
.DS_Store
.*
***#
*~
*__pycache__
**.pyc
**.ipynb_checkpoints
*.pdf
cache/
tmp/

# Input and output data
```

```
.snakemake/
raw_data/
intermediary_data/
data_assets/
assets/
metadata/
!*/.git_keep
```

Including data files in the `.gitignore` file early in the development process, even before starting to test the workflow with data, is important, because if data files are accidentally committed to the repository, then everyone who downloads the repository will need to download them: even if a later commit removes the files again, they will still be present in the history. (It is possible to rewrite history to remove unwanted files, but this takes additional work and requires coordination to not reintroduce them.)

4.1.5 `.pre-commit-config.yaml`

We aim for our releases to be useful for others, and to minimise the work needed when we are developing them. As such, we try to make our code easy to read; it is difficult enough to read one's own code after a few weeks of not looking at it, let alone someone else's. To this end, we use some basic automated code quality checks, to keep the basic formatting of code consistent.

For this, we make use of PRE-COMMIT [25]. When inside a repository, with PRE-COMMIT available in the `$PATH`, running the command

```
pre-commit install
```

adds a hook to the repository that is run when a commit is attempted; it reads and runs the checks defined in `.pre-commit-config.yaml`, and if any checks do not pass, the commit is blocked. Some checks automatically fix the files such that you can retry the commit quickly; other checks might require manual fixes to be made.

A minimal `.pre-commit-config.yaml` for our work might be:

```
default_language_version:
  python: python3.12
repos:
- repo: https://github.com/astral-sh/ruff-pre-commit
  rev: v0.5.1
  hooks:
    - id: ruff
      # Lint rules suggested by ruff docs, just for starters:
      args: [--fix]
    - id: ruff-format
- repo: https://github.com/pre-commit/pre-commit-hooks
  rev: v4.6.0
  hooks:
    - id: check-yaml
    - id: end-of-file-fixer
    - id: trailing-whitespace
    - id: check-toml
    - id: mixed-line-ending
- repo: https://github.com/jumanjihouse/pre-commit-hooks
  rev: 3.0.0
  hooks:
    - id: markdownlint
      files: "content/"
```

The versions specified are correct at time of writing, but are likely out of date by the time you read this document. You *may* use PRE-COMMIT CI [26] to keep these up to date.

4.2 Workflow management

Performing an analysis in lattice quantum field theory has many moving parts. We typically work with many ensembles, for each of which we compute many observables. We want to combine subsets of each of these in different ways, and perform various fits of them. Each analysis step takes a different amount of time, and depends on others having been previously completed.

As discussed above, we require that a single command be able to reproduce the full analysis, end to end. One way we might start thinking about that is by writing a shell script, to run the various

tools needed in order. We might also consider using a single Python script that calls the various functions that we need to run, using subprocesses where we use non-Python tools. However, this comes with some limitations: if we want to run multiple steps in parallel (as we likely want to, as the number of steps grows), we need to manually specify how and where to parallelise. And if we want to avoid recomputing (potentially expensive) steps that we have already completed and whose inputs have not changed, we need to manually perform these checks.

To avoid reinventing the wheel, we instead choose to build on the work of others who have already solved these problems. A workflow manager is a tool that allows you to specify a set of rules for how to compute specific outputs given specific inputs; when given a specific target to generate, it identifies what steps need to be performed, and performs them. A typical workflow manager does this by building a directed acyclic graph (DAG) of the steps; this then allows it to parallelise over all steps that do not directly depend on each other.

After a survey of the available options, we identified SNAKEMAKE [27] as a good fit for our typical needs. It has a number of features that are useful to us:

- It can run on one or multiple CPU cores.
- It can manage the software environments needed for running rules using Conda. No manual installation of environments is necessary for a user of the release, beyond installing Snakemake.
- It tracks what outputs it has generated using what inputs, so only re-runs rules when the input data change.
- The syntax for rule definitions is built on top of Python, so is extensible if the standard syntax does not meet our needs

It can also run parts of a workflow on external HPC resources; this is not a feature we currently use, but might be useful in future.

Currently, there are no Snakemake tutorials specific to the lattice context; while it is our ambition to change this, for the time being, we refer to e.g. Refs. [28, 29].

4.2.1 Structuring a workflow

The benefits of a workflow manager discussed above are maximised when the structure of the workflow is aligned with the strengths of the workflow manager. Put shortly:

- The scope of each tool (or rule) *should* be kept as small as possible, with the complexity being encoded as relationships between rules in the workflow definition.
- Parameters *should* be known to the workflow manager, rather than passing a file containing them.
- Input and output files *should* be specified as command-line parameters, rather than being hard-coded.
- The workflow *should not* append to files, only create them afresh. If joining files together is needed, that *should* be its own rule.

To take a concrete example, if we have data files for meson correlation functions and gradient flow histories at various values of the bare mass am_0 , and we wish to plot the masses of the pseudoscalar and vector mesons aM_{PS} and aM_V , normalised by the gradient flow scale w_0/a as a function of am_0 , then the workflow might be structured as the following:

- A preamble, in which the workflow reads a metadata file with information about the ensembles, and in particular the plateau positions for each channel for each ensemble.
- A rule to take one ensemble’s gradient flow history, and output bootstrap samples for w_0/a to a file, labelled by an ensemble identifier and the observable name (for example, `Sp4nF2b6.7mF-0.62T48L32/w0_samples.json`). This file *should* also carry metadata and provenance information about the ensemble.
- A rule to take one ensemble’s meson correlation function data, and using the plateau position metadata, compute the mass of one mesonic channel aM_X , outputting bootstrap samples to a file, labelled by an ensemble identifier and the channel name (for example, `Sp4nF2b6.7mF-0.62T48L32/ps_mass_samples.json`).

This file *should* also carry metadata and provenance information about the ensemble.

- A rule to take the bootstrap samples for aM_X and w_0/a , and output the dimensionless product $\hat{M}_X = w_0 M_X$, to a file labelled by an ensemble identifier and a description of the product (for example, `Sp4nF2b6.7mF-0.62T48L32/normalised_ps_mass_samples.json`). This file *should* also carry metadata and provenance information about the ensemble.

- A rule to take any number of files each containing the value of the normalised mass for a single ensemble, and a plot style definition, and output a plot of the normalised mass against the bare fermion mass (the latter obtained from the metadata).

To meet the requirements discussed in Section 3 above, there would also want to be a rule to take all of the various sample files and output a CSV that could be included in the data release.

4.3 Structuring the repository

We have discussed above the essential files to include in the root directory of the repository. Now, let's go into more detail about how to structure the remainder of the repository.

- Files relating to the definition of the workflow *should* be placed in a `workflow/` directory. The workflow itself *must* be placed in `workflow/Snakefile`. Workflows with many rules *should* be split into modules; these *should* be placed in `workflow/rules/`. Conda environment definitions *should* be placed in `workflow/envs/`. This structure matches the standard recommendations for Snakemake projects in general.
- Source files *should* be placed in a `src/` directory. For projects of any complexity, this *should* be structured as a Python package, containing an `__init__.py` file, so that relative imports can be made.
- Definitions of, for example, plot styles *should* be placed in a `styles/` directory.
- Libraries that are not available via standard package repositories *should* be placed in a `libs/` directory, as discussed below.
- Input data *should* be placed in a `raw_data/` directory. This directory *may* contain a `.git_keep` file so that it is created when the repository is cloned, but all other files in the directory *must* be ignored in `.gitignore`, to avoid accidentally committing large amounts of data.
- Data that have been quoted from other publications that did not provide a data release (so where numbers had to be transcribed by hand) *should* be placed in a `quoted_data/` directory. They *must* include documentation as to their provenance, including attribution to the original authors.
- Files containing metadata and analysis parameters *should* be placed in a `metadata/` directory. This directory *may* contain a `.git_keep` file, but all other files in the directory *must* be ignored in `.gitignore`.
- Data produced by the workflow but not intended for distribution (for example, the bootstrap sample files discussed above) *should* be placed in an `intermediary_data/` directory. This directory *must not* contain a `.git_keep` file, and *must* be ignored in `.gitignore`.
- Data produced by the workflow and intended for distribution (for example, CSV files of final numbers to include in the data release) *should* be placed in a `data_assets/` directory. This directory *may* contain a `.git_keep` file, particularly if it is anticipated that users will place files into the directory by hand, but all other files in the directory *must* be ignored in `.gitignore`, to avoid accidentally committing large amounts of data.
- Outputs generated by the workflow for inclusion in a manuscript (plots, tables, and variable definitions) *should* be placed into an `assets/` directory. This directory *may* contain a `.git_keep` file, but all other files in the directory *must* be ignored in `.gitignore`. When preparing a manuscript, the directory *should* be copied directly into the project; when re-running the workflow, the previous version *should* be deleted from the project before the updated version is copied in.

A template repository with this structure, including templates for the *required* files listed in Section 4.1, is provided at Ref. [30].

4.3.1 Libraries

For published libraries, it is typically sufficient to allow Conda to install them from standard repositories, such as PyPI for Python packages. For libraries only made available via GitHub or similar forge services, these *must not* be specified via a GitHub (or similar) URL, for the same reason we do not use GitHub to publish our workflows—GitHub does not provide a guarantee of long-term stability.

Instead, where libraries are internal and/or sufficiently actively developed that they are not available via a package repository, these *must* be included as Git submodules, and installed directly from the local copy. We place local copies of libraries in a `libs` directory.

To download a repository as a submodule, use the syntax

```
mkdir -p libs
cd libs
git submodule add https://github.com/username/reponame
```

This addition can then be committed to the repository as usual. Note that the URL used *must* be a publicly-accessible HTTPS address, not a private repository or a `git@github.com:` SSH address.

To clone a repository that includes submodules, use

```
git clone --recurse-submodules git@github.com:telos-collaboration/workflow_name
```

When adding a submodule to a repository for the first time, the `README` *should* be updated to include this instruction in place of the plain `git clone` that would otherwise be present.

To specify a local copy of a library in a Conda environment specification, replace the `library_name==0.0.1` or similar specification generated by `conda env export` with `.././libs/library_name`.

Note that when GitHub exports a ZIP file of a repository, it does not include the contents of any submodules. As such, we *must* create our own ZIP files of such repositories when uploading to Zenodo.

4.4 Assets to generate

In general, the workflow *should* generate four broad classes of output: plots, tables, definitions, and data assets.

When naming files, the workflow *must not* generate files with the same name in different directories. This is because arXiv only partially supports subdirectories; while it can compile projects with files in subdirectories, if two files in different subdirectories have the same name, neither is accessible to LaTeX, and the compilation fails.

4.4.1 Plots

Plot generation is one of the first tasks researchers approach automating. A full deep dive into automated plotting is outside the scope of this document, but we will highlight some key points specific to the way that we work.

- Plots *should* be produced using Matplotlib, or a tool based on its engine.
- Plots *should* read in style information from a common style file, and *should not* have excessive cosmetic overrides.
- The workflow *should* make it simple to change which plot style file is in use, for example, to switch to using sans-serif fonts and a dark background for presentation slides.
- Plots *should* use a standard colour cycle, to maximise accessibility for those with colourblindness.
- Similarly, where possible, plots *should* use differing markers in addition to colours, to aid colourblind readers and those with black and white printers in interpreting them correctly. Where necessary, plots *may* use markers and colours to differentiate different degrees of freedom.
- Plots *should* use the `layout="constrained"` option to `plt.figure` (or to `plt.subplots`) to maximise the use of space.
- Plots *should* specify a `figsize` equal to the anticipated size in the final manuscript, so that they can be used in LaTeX without specifying the `\width` option. This ensures that font sizes remain consistent and legible.
- Plots *should* be included in LaTeX files using syntax like:

```
\includegraphics{assets/plots/spectrum}
```

The `width=` argument *should not* be specified, and *should not* need to be.

- Axis and other labels on plots *must* match the notation used in the main text.
- Where the caption of a figure depends on the specific parameters used to generate it, then a `.tex` file *should* also be generated containing the caption, or a definition file generated as described in Section 1.5. For example, if the workflow generates a plot `spectrum_beta2.3.pdf`, it would also generate a file `spectrum_beta2.3_figure.tex`, containing something along the lines of

```
\begin{figure}
  \includegraphics{assets/plots/spectrum_beta2.3}
  \caption{\label{fig:spectrum-betatwopointthree}
  The spectrum of the theory at  $\beta=2.3$ }
\end{figure}
```

In this instance, the figure *should* be included in the manuscript using

```
\input{assets/plots/spectrum_beta2.3_figure.tex}
```

- Plots *should* be placed in an `assets/plots/` directory.

4.4.2 Tables

Tables are frequently constructed by hand, or generated using tools but then copied and pasted into a manuscript. This manual intervention is error prone, and increases the likelihood that the work presented will not be reproducible, due to numbers from different iterations of the workflow (or other numbers entirely, from typographical errors) being mixed into the final manuscript.

- There *must* be a 1:1 correspondence between tables and `.tex` files generated. That is, each table *must* be in its own `.tex` file.
- Each table file *must* contain the entire table, starting with `\begin{tabular}` (or equivalent) and ending with `\end{tabular}` (or equivalent).
- Where the caption of the table depends on data presented therein, the workflow *should* also include the caption in the `.tex` file. The file *should* then contain the entire `table` environment, starting with `\begin{table}` and ending with `\end{table}`.
- Table files *must* be included in the manuscript using commands along the lines of

```
\input{assets/tables/spectrum_table.tex}
```
- Tables generated by a single workflow *must* follow the same formatting conventions, in particular around where to place vertical and horizontal lines. Where possible, this *should* be achieved by making use of common functions, allowing style changes to be made by changing a single definition.
- Table definitions *should* be preceded by metadata describing them and their provenance. This *must* be formatted as LaTeX comments (i.e. lines beginning with `%`).
- Tables *should* be placed in an `assets/tables/` directory.

How to generate tables programmatically For plain tables of numbers without uncertainties, Pandas DataFrames have a `styler.to_latex` method to enable this. For tables of numbers with uncertainties, this method *may* be used in conjunction with the `FORMAT_MULTIPLE_ERRORS` [31] library. Where horizontal lines are needed to break up sections of a table, currently this is challenging to achieve with Pandas, but a pull request is open that is hoped to enable this in future.

4.4.3 Definitions

Frequently, we want to discuss numerical results in our papers, including quoting the numbers themselves. Our first temptation might be to write the number in the text manually. However, if during drafting, an additional data point is added that changes a fit result in the second decimal place, it is easy for these numbers to become inconsistent with the actual analysis results.

To avoid this, our workflows *should* output definitions of LaTeX commands that can be used in documents as placeholders for the numbers, that will then be filled in by the workflow. For example, our workflow might define a command

```
\newcommand\PSMassContinuum{0.1234(56)(78)}
```

which would then be used in the text as

We find the mass of the pseudoscalar in the continuum limit to be `\PSMassContinuum`.

which would in turn render in the document as

“We find the mass of the pseudoscalar in the continuum limit to be 0.1234(56)(78).”

- Definitions *should* be produced for all numbers presented with uncertainties in a manuscript.
- Where definitions have been produced, they *must* be used in place of all instances of the relevant number.
- Definitions *should not* force math mode, since in some instances they might be used inside a larger mathematical environment. (They *may* use `\ensuremath`.)
- Definition files *must* have the `.tex` extension.
- Definition files *should* be placed in an `assets/definitions/` directory.
- Each definition file *should* begin with metadata describing the definitions and their provenance. This *must* be formatted as LaTeX comments (i.e. lines beginning with `%`).
- Definition files *must* be loaded in the preamble of the manuscript LaTeX document, along the lines

```
\input{assets/definitions/spectrum_definitions.tex}
```

4.5 Metadata and provenance tracking

It is useful when files are taken outside of their original context to be able to identify where they came from. A full realisation of this would require implementing something like PROV [32], as has been done by the authors of Ref. [33]; this is beyond our current capacity, but *should* be on our roadmap. However, retaining a subset of provenance information still has value. This *may* be “stamped” as a comment in a file, and/or included as an additional file.

- When storing intermediary results, particularly when JSON or similar formats are used, files *should* also store structured metadata and provenance information.
- When producing tables and definition files, these *should* also include unstructured metadata and provenance information in LaTeX comments.
- When producing figures as PDF files, including provenance information is non-trivial, and is currently considered out of scope. When producing other formats (for example, Scalable Vector Graphics), provenance information *may* be included as a comment.
- When producing directories of output (for example, `assets/`), there *should* be a machine-readable (for example, JSON) file placed at its root indicating metadata and provenance specific to the workflow run that produced it.

Things to include in a provenance stamp will vary from case to case, but *should* most likely include:

- A comment warning that the asset was/assets were automatically generated, and *should not* be directly modified, but instead that the workflow *should* be re-run. This *should* be sorted to appear at the top of the listing.
- The commit ID of the workflow used to generate the asset, and if there were uncommitted changes present.
- The time at which the asset was generated.
- The computer using which the asset was generated.
- The person who ran the workflow. (For example, their username.)
- For assets generated from other data, the files that were used as input.
- Parameters that were used in the generation of the asset.

Basic provenance tracking for many of these, and annotation of output assets with them, is implemented in Ref. [34]; this *may* be reused rather than reimplementing the functionality from scratch.

4.6 Standard tools and techniques

As discussed above, we make use of Snakemake for workflow management. Since Snakemake invokes rules using shell commands, it is relatively simple to coordinate tools written in different languages. However, increasing the number of languages increases the complexity of reading and understanding the code, and of setting up a working environment, so where possible, workflows *should* use a common language, and failing that, as few languages as possible. In most instances, new workflow components *should* be written in PYTHON.

Authors of workflows *should* reuse existing code where practical, rather than rewriting a slightly different version. This helps to maintain consistency between equivalent data presented in different publications.

Where there are common elements used in many workflows, these *should* be grouped into a common library, to be imported by each workflow. This avoids having duplicate copies of an analysis in different workflows, each with slight differences. For example, rather than each workflow defining its own method of solving the Generalised Eigenvalue Problem (or worse, different parts of the same workflow but written by different collaborators having different implementations), there *should* be a common library for the aspects that are common across applications.

Workflows *should* aim to be “DRY” (“don’t repeat yourself”; as opposed to “WET”, “write everything twice”). Significant amounts of copy-pasting of blocks of code, or entire files, *should* be avoided; instead, common functionality *should* be abstracted to a single place.

4.6.1 Code review

Many of the above points require relatively fluency with the language being used, and some meditation on aspects of research software engineering. There is no substitute for experience and fluency with a language; this is gained through experience and feedback.

One way to gain this feedback is through code review. Where a workflow is being developed collaboratively by multiple people, changes to the workflow *should* be developed in branches, and then submitted to the main branch as pull requests. Feedback *should* then be given on the content of the pull request by another co-author of the workflow. Feedback *must* be constructive and positive. The pull requester and the reviewer *should* come to an agreement on the course of action to take before merging the pull request, and any identified changes *should* be completed before the pull request is merged.

Where the workflow is being developed by a single author, code review *may* instead be done as part of the workflow testing process; see Sec. 4.8 below.

4.6.2 Statistics and fits

Unless there is a strong reason not to, we make use of bootstrap sampling to obtain bias-free uncertainty estimates in our work. (In the majority of our work to date, we have used 200 bootstrap samples for each analysis. However, as we begin performing higher-precision computations with more statistics, it might be beneficial to use higher numbers of bootstrap samples.) We make use of LSQFIT [35, 36] and CORRFITTER [37, 38] for performing fits of data and correlation functions in our work.

4.6.3 Continuous Integration

To reduce the amount of data that collaboration members need to have on their own machine, which has grown larger over time, and to make it easier to set up a standardised software environment, we aim to set up a platform that makes use of Data Version Control [39] or similar to manage versions of input data for analysis, and that integrates with GitHub Actions, to automatically run workflows on centralised infrastructure.

Currently this is still in the early planning phases, but once ready, the output from this system *should* be used as the authoritative version of assets to include in publications. Workflows *should* still be tested by other collaboration members to ensure portability and reproducibility.

4.7 Numerical reproducibility

While in Sec. 1.5.1 we define reproducibility in black and white, there are in fact certain degrees to which data are reproducible. They might give compatible results within error bars, or might give identical results down to the last bit, or something in between.

An analysis workflow *should* give bitwise identical output, except for differences in headers and other provenance data, when run on the same platform, with the same parallelisation options. It *must* give compatible results, with differences much smaller¹ than the statistical error, when re-run, including running on other machines or with different parallelisations.

4.7.1 Randomness

Analysis workflows frequently make use of randomness. In particular, bootstrap sampling always uses randomness, and for a finite number of bootstrap samples, the final numbers obtained will have an in principle negligible but noticeable dependence on the choice of random numbers. As such, we *must* fix random seeds before performing a computation with randomness. This *must* be done separately for each workflow rule; since the workflow can execute in any order compatible with the data dependencies, different runs might otherwise give different results.

Random seeds *must* be different for each ensemble, since otherwise correlations are introduced between them. In order to avoid hardcoding specific random seeds, which could raise questions in the minds of readers of our workflows (“Where did that number come from?” “Was it chosen to give a specific outcome?”), we generate seeds deterministically from input metadata. To introduce sufficient entropy into these, it is *recommended* to use a hash of the ensemble name as the random seed. This has the benefit that having the same bootstrap samples for different observables is simplified.

An example Python implementation might look like:

```
import hashlib
import numpy as np
```

¹We deliberately do not explicitly define “much smaller” at this time.

```
def get_rng(ensemble_name):
    ensemble_hash = hashlib.md5(ensemble_name.encode("utf8")).digest()
    seed = abs(int.from_bytes(filename_hash, "big"))
    return np.random.default_rng(seed)
```

This approach will give results that are reproducible to near-machine precision.

4.8 Testing a workflow

Before a workflow is published, it *must* be tested by a collaboration member and coauthor other than the one who wrote it. It is *recommended* that the tester and workflow author use different platforms, to identify potential cross-platform issues. For example, if the author used macOS to develop the workflow, it is *recommended* for the tester to use GNU/Linux.

The tester *must* be given access to only the files that will be submitted to Zenodo and arXiv (the raw data, metadata and parameters, and output CSVs from the data release, the source code archive from the analysis workflow release, and the generated assets that will be included in the article). In the first instance, they *must not* be supervised or guided during the author during this process. They *must* run the workflow end-to-end, by following the instructions in the workflow `README`, and verify that the assets (plots, tables, definitions, and CSVs) are correctly reproduced.

If difficulties with setting up or running the workflow are encountered, the tester *may* reach out to the author for assistance, and *should* provide feedback to the author. If the issue is specific to the workflow (rather than, for example, a general difficulty installing Snakemake), the author *should* update the documentation to give more guidance around the difficult aspect.

If the workflow runs, but does not correctly reproduce the output, this *must* be fed back to the author. The author *may* work with the tester to identify the cause of the discrepancy, and the divergence *must* be fixed before the workflow and data are published.

Once the tester is able to run the workflow end to end and obtain compatible results with the author's, the workflow *may* be published.

4.9 Publishing a workflow

It is not sufficient to link to a GitHub repository from a journal article. GitHub provides no guarantees of long-term stability of repositories, or even of the addresses to them. Instead, similarly to data releases, we *must* publish workflows using a service that provides a persistent identifier, and a commitment to long-term availability.

At time of writing, the TELOS Collaboration publishes its workflows using Zenodo [17].

After a release has been published, the repository *may* still be used for ongoing work. For example, if a referee requests changes requiring modifications to the analysis workflow, these *must* be made in the same repository. These changes *must* be released on Zenodo, as a new version of the same record as above, before the paper is published. If work continues on a direct followup paper, the new paper's analysis *should* be a direct continuation of the original's, in the same repository, and *should* be published as a new version of the same record.

4.9.1 Preparing an archive

In principle, one could connect GitHub with Zenodo, and automatically generate a record from a GitHub Release. However, as discussed above, this does not include the contents of submodules, meaning that the archives downloaded from the release would not be usable.

To ensure that all submodules are correctly included in the release, we *should* clone a fresh copy of the repository, and archive it, keeping only the working copy, i.e. excluding the `.git` directories:

```
mkdir tmp
cd tmp
git clone --recurse-submodules git@github.com:telos-collaboration/workflow_name
zip -9 --exclude "**/.git/*" --exclude "**/.git" -r workflow_name workflow_name
```

One *may* instead work from the existing working copy, but in this case they *must* first strip out all data not in the repository, for example using `git clean`. Data from the data release *must not* be included in the workflow release.

4.9.2 What to include in a release

The release *should* include two files:

- The README file from the repository, which *should* also form the basis of the Zenodo description, and
- The ZIP archive of the repository.

4.9.3 Completing the upload form

The procedure for this is largely the same as that used for data releases, described in Sec. 3.2, with the following exceptions:

- The Resource Type *should* be “Workflow”.
- The Title *should* be the title of the corresponding article, followed by “—Analysis workflow”.
- The License *should* match the one agreed and specified in the repository.
- In addition to the preprint and published version, the Related works *must* refer to the data release, with relation “requires”.
- The Software section *must* include
 - A link to the GitHub repository under the `telos-collaboration` organisation.
 - A listing of the programming languages used, which are likely to minimally include PYTHON and SNAKEMAKE.
 - The Development Status “Inactive”.

5 HPC Software

This area has to date received less focus than the topics of the preceding sections of this document; as such, many elements described as “*should*” are aspirational rather than describing current practice.

5.1 Open Source and Community Software

The TELOS collaboration has benefited greatly from open source and community software for HPC. We have made extensive use of HiRep [40, 41], Grid [42, 43], and Hadrons [44, 45]. It is incumbent on us to not only be passive consumers of this software, but also to give back in support of its continued development and sustainability.

All publications making use of a piece of software *must* specify what software was used, and what version. Where we have made modifications to a piece of software for our use case, these modifications *must* be publicly available. In the absence of this, others will not be able to reproduce our work, and the software’s authors will not be able to correctly judge the reach and impact of their work. In principle, there *should* be a Zenodo release of the specific version used, to ensure that there is a persistent identifier and long term retention; however, to date this has not been done due to a lack of clarity around appropriate authorship for the resulting Zenodo record.

After making a change to a piece of software, the developer *should* think carefully about whether it is valuable for the change to be fed back to the upstream repository. In instances where the change is likely to be an obstruction to others’ use cases, this is likely not a good idea, but if the change is neutral or positive, then minimally, the change *should* be proposed to the upstream maintainer. If the original author is amenable, then a pull request (or equivalent) *should* be submitted, and appropriate work done in collaboration with the maintainer to bring the work to a mergeable state. (The change *may* also be proposed directly in the form of a pull request.)

Where changes need to be maintained separately, we *must* retain these changes in a local fork of the repository. The number of different local forks of a repository *should* be minimised; where possible, changes *should* be merged into a single main branch, and where this is impractical, versions *should* be retained as branches of a single repository.

5.2 Data formats

In general, software running on HPC *should* output data in a format easily ingested by downstream tooling, and easily shared in a FAIR way. This *may* be in addition to text-based logs; the logs *should* however not be the only data output format.

More specifically,

- Software generating configurations *should* output field configurations in the ILDG binary format [46], and corresponding metadata in the QCDml [47]². At time of writing, in the versions

²An update to these to support higher representations and gauge groups beyond SU(3) is in preparation at time of writing, but is anticipated to become available very shortly.

in use within the TELOS Collaboration, neither Grid nor HiRep is able to do this; HiRep cannot write the ILDG format at all³, instead using its own format exclusively, while Grid can write it but does not set relevant metadata correctly.

- Software performing observable computations on configurations *should* output the results in HDF5, JSON, or XML format, with sufficient and appropriate metadata to identify the ensemble and computation performed. At time of writing, Hadrons is able to output in HDF5 and XML format, but the specific metadata output are not sufficient for our use case. Grid can in principle output these formats, but the tools we make use of do not do this. HiRep has support for JSON in certain tools in certain forks, but our production version does not support this.

5.3 Workflows

Historically, a typical HPC workflow has involved setting up some or all of:

- Writing or adjusting job scripts and input files individually for each ensemble,
- Manually changing input files after successive jobs,
- Handcrafting AWK scripts at the command line to check progress and acceptance,
- Regularly resubmitting jobs as time limits on running jobs elapse,
- Writing fragile shell scripts to automate one or more aspects of the above,
- Needing to cancel and resubmit jobs due to an error introduced by one of the above.

None of these is desirable; they are all a drain on time that could have been spent more productively, they are all barriers to reproducibility, and they all have the potential to partially or totally invalidate claimed results. For example, neglecting to switch the `rlx_start` flag from `new` to `continue` in HiRep introduces sizeable autocorrelations when running the RHMC algorithm.

To avoid these issues, we *should* have two additional tools available to us: a HMC launcher/monitor (tentatively called `hmcDJ`) and a job coordinator (`PLATESPINNER`). At time of writing, neither of these is written; we discuss below some requirements to inform their development.

5.3.1 `hmcDJ`

The anticipated responsibilities of this software are:

- Read parameters specifying the ensemble from a file in a standard format (for example, JSON).
- Identify whether configurations already exist matching these parameters, and resume from this if so. Otherwise, start from a cold, warm, or hot configuration as specified.
- Be able to start a new chain by resuming from a checkpoint but re-seeding the random number generator.
- Be able to track acceptance of the algorithm over time, adjust this automatically during a thermalisation period, and raise warnings and refuse to continue if it remains unacceptably low or if it changes outside of the thermalisation period.
- Save provenance and metadata with each configuration, as discussed above. This *should* make it clear, for example, at what point a secondary chain branched off its parent, and when parameters such as the trajectory length were adjusted.
- Seed the generator deterministically from the ensemble parameters, while still providing sufficient entropy to maintain statistical independence of ensembles.
- Monitor the time taken to complete each trajectory, read the remaining time in a job from the environment, and if there will be insufficient time to complete the next trajectory, checkpoint and quit cleanly instead.
- Based on this, be able to provide an estimate of the notice needed from the scheduler to cleanly quit, and take advantage of shorter allocations by allowing preemption with sufficient notice. Listen for interrupt signals from the scheduler, and checkpoint and cleanly exit after the end of the current trajectory in this case.

Grid's HMC implementation satisfies some but not all of these requirements. We anticipate that `hmcDJ` could be written as a thin wrapper around Grid's HMC class.

³The HiRep binary format is compatible with the configuration data portion of the ILDG binary format in some instances.

5.3.2 PlateSpinner

A difficulty with some HPC systems is that HMC is not parallel in Monte Carlo time, and so one job in a sequence cannot start before the previous one completes. To avoid jobs starting and then needing to immediately abort, this ultimately means that successive jobs cannot begin queuing until their predecessors complete. This means there can be significant downtime between successive jobs in a sequence, making it more difficult to obtain the desired statistics in a given time.

However, where many ensembles are being generated concurrently, at the point where a single HPC job starts, it is likely that one of the ensembles is not being actively generated, or that there is analysis work on one or more ensembles outstanding. To this end, we anticipate PLATESPINNER will in its most basic form:

- Be launched at the start of each job on the machine.
- Read a database of target generation workloads, from the HMC DJ input files.
- Identify which of these workloads are already running.
- If there is a workload not already running, which is compatible with the job's resources (i.e. not so large as to run out of memory, or so small as to give very poor parallelisation), start it.
- If all generation workloads are already running, identify analysis workloads that are outstanding, and not already running, and start one of these.
- Repeat the previous step until the anticipated runtime exceeds the remaining time for the job.

In addition to the above, our work utilises machines with GPU resources. Most such machines also have a non-negligible number of CPU cores available. Typically, the majority of these cores are not utilised by the GPU workloads. Some of our analysis workloads are not able to efficiently utilise GPUs, so require CPU resources. Tests show that these can be run concurrently on the same nodes as our GPU workloads without affecting the performance of the latter. This gives significantly better utilisation of the resources, both in terms of resource time allocation and in terms of total energy utilisation. We anticipate that PLATESPINNER will also manage this process.

The requirements for PLATESPINNER are similar to the capabilities of TAXI [48]; however, the latter appears more tightly coupled to HMC generation with the specific tooling used by the authors of Ref. [48].

6 Acknowledgements

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Open access statement For the purpose of open access, the authors have applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising.

Data Availability Statement No new data were produced in preparation or in support of this work.

Software Availability Statement No new software was produced in preparation or in support of this work.

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A Checklist for publishing a journal article

In this Appendix is a checklist that *should* be completed for all publications. Underneath each high-level goal (circles) is a set of tasks that *should* be completed before the goal can be completed (squares).

- Circulate draft to collaboration
 - DOI for data release obtained and added to draft
 - DOI for analysis release obtained and added to draft
 - Hand-generated provisional/placeholder plots marked
 - Software used is committed to version control
 - Software names and versions (e.g. commit IDs) are specified
 - Rights retention statement is present
 - Data availability statement is present
 - Software availability statement is present
- Publish data release
 - README contains data format descriptions for all files
 - Raw data are all included
 - CSVs are present for all data presented in paper (tabulated or plotted)
 - Archives do not contain unwanted files (e.g. operating system metadata files like `.DS_Store`)
 - Release cross-checked with analysis workflow by another collaboration member
- Publish analysis workflow
 - README includes requirements installation instructions
 - README includes instructions for getting input data
 - README includes instructions for running workflow
 - README notes expected run time of workflow
 - No data are hardcoded into code. (Check for any numbers with more than three significant figures.)
 - Quoted data carry appropriate attribution
 - Software environment is specified in one or more `.yaml` files
 - Workflow runs end to end from a single command without errors
 - Workflow archive does not include any unwanted files (e.g. data files, or operating system metadata files like `.DS_Store`)
 - Workflow cross-checked with data release by another collaboration member
 - GitHub repository is public
- Publish pre-print on arXiv
 - `author.xml` written, validated against schema, and included in source package
 - Data release public (*optional*)
 - Analysis workflow release public (*optional*)
 - Final analysis workflow is committed to version control
 - All plots, tables, and quoted numbers generated from workflow. No placeholder markers remain.
 - All assets regenerated from a clean workflow run
- Submit manuscript to journal
 - Preprint added to website
 - arXiv paper password forwarded to coauthors
- Submit corrected manuscript to journal after implementing referee feedback
 - If changes have been made to analysis or presentation, all assets regenerated from a clean workflow run.
 - Updated analysis workflow is committed to version control
- Proofs are approved with journal, article is published
 - Author Accepted Manuscript uploaded to institutional repository (e.g. Cronfa)
 - Finalised data release public (*required*)
 - Finalised analysis workflow release public (*required*)

- If updated data/workflow releases published, manuscript updated to point to DOI of updated version.
- Publication process finalised
 - Website updated with published article
 - Institutional repository (e.g. Cronfa) updated with journal details

B Applying these techniques outside of lattice

The guidance in this document has been written with the context of lattice quantum field theory in mind, as well as the specific requirements and capabilities of the TELOS Collaboration. For other contexts, there is a wide range of advice available; for example, The Turing Way [4] provides tools and techniques applicable across much of data science and research software, while OpenML [49] provides tooling and resources for open research using machine learning techniques.

That said, there is a subset of the advice presented here that can be summarised to form a minimal set of principles applicable, for example, in work in theoretical physics not on the lattice.

B.1 Data

If a publication generates new data, these data *must* be released openly, citably, and in machine-readable form. “Data” in this context includes:

- One or more numbers with error bars,
- One or more points plotted on a graph,
- Numbers needing a data table to display in a paper, and
- Coefficients in equations with more than a handful of terms.

As a rule of thumb, if numbers would be useful for others, and taking it from the text of the paper would be laborious or result in loss of precision, then it is data and *must* be released.

These numbers *must* be shared in CSV format, unless there is a strong reason to do otherwise. It is worth thinking carefully about how to combine related data to minimise the number of separate files that a reader has to work with; this might differ from the native representations you currently use. Where a metadata schema is available, this *must* be followed to ensure interoperability and reusability; regardless, a common format for data between publications *should* be aimed for. The guidance in Section 3.1.1 provides more detail on this.

The data release *must* also include documentation so that the data consumer is able to make use of it. A plain-text, human-readable (for example, Markdown) **README** file *should* be designed as the first (and potentially only) place a reader looks. The **README** *must* provide at least a link to the paper presenting the data, and a listing describing the contents of each file in the release. It *must* either describe or link to documentation describing the data formats of the other files in the release. Section 3.1.6 discusses in more detail how to approach this.

The data release *must* be published in a repository that commits to long-term availability and that offers a persistent identifier, such as Zenodo [17], which by default allows 50GiB and 100 files per dataset. One *may* obtain a DOI from Zenodo to include in a manuscript in advance of publishing the data; details on this are in Section 3.2.2. Section 3.2.4 provides a brief guide to completing the Zenodo upload form for lattice data.

B.2 Workflows

A first step in the direction of open workflows is to share the tools needed to translate from the data shared in the data release to the outputs in the publication (plots, tables, etc., as discussed in Section 4.4); this allows a reader to better understand the data formats, and to at least verify that the data do indeed give the presented results. If shared in this way, it likely makes more sense to include this as a part of the data release, rather than releasing a separate workflow, as the workflow only makes sense in the context of the data it was written against.

However, as discussed in Section 4, to fully ensure reproducibility, sharing the full software workflow to go from input data to output data is needed. This is something always worth striving for, even if sometimes one falls short, for example, due to not having permission to publish one or more tools that were shared privately by a colleague.

When it is possible to share the full workflow, this *should* give bitwise identical results (aside from differences in metadata around, for example, when the run was executed) when re-run on the same platform with the same parallelisation options, and *must* give compatible results when re-run anywhere. (See Section 4.7 for additional detail.) Before it is published, it *must* be tested end to end from a fresh start; this *should* be done by a co-author who did not perform the original analysis. More details on how to approach this are in Section 4.8.

More generally, those working on workflows *should* review the work of others and have their work reviewed in turn, as discussed in Section 4.6.1, to enable the spread of good practice. When planning new work, it is *recommended* to adopt version control and good practices for repository structure (discussed in Sections 4.1 and 4.3), and to consider utilising a workflow manager (see Section 4.2), to handle the flow of data between different tools, without needing to reinvent the wheel.

B.3 Publications

Aside from mentions of high-performance computing which might not be relevant, all of the discussion of Section 2 applies more widely. Specifically, all narrative work *should* be released under a Creative Commons license; rights retention statements *may* be used to ensure that this is permitted. If work is not funded by UKRI, then details of requirements for open access *must* be checked with funders, to ensure that any rights retention statements are valid. An `author.xml` file *may* be used to assist in providing metadata to indexing services like INSPIRE. Software, computing resources, open data, and data storage resources *must* be acknowledged, in addition to funders and those who have provided useful discussions Software and Data Availability Statements *must* be added after the acknowledgments.